

**Tissue Engineering and Additive Manufacturing – 3D Printing:
Creation of a digital cranial bone implant model**

*A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the
degree of MSc in Engineering Management*

by

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DECLARATION

I certify that all material in this dissertation *which is not my own* work has been identified and appropriate acknowledgement and referencing has been provided. I also certify that no material is included for which a degree has previously been conferred upon me.

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Abstract

Tissue Engineering is the science whose object is the physiological regeneration of a biological tissue in laboratory conditions (in vitro) and directly in patients (in vivo). The physiological regeneration is achieved through the cultivation of the patient's cells inside tissue scaffolds. The scaffolds are the "womb," inside of which, the cells multiply and are supported, in order to regenerate tissue, while the scaffold decomposes into non-toxic by-products. The successful decomposition of the scaffolds, during the development of the tissue, is based on the use of biomaterials, particularly polymers, which share the same attributes in biocompatibility and biodegradability.

The tissue scaffolds are manufactured using many methods, and among them are rapid prototyping techniques, that manufacture the scaffolds in layers. The most common among them is Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), 3D Printing, and Stereolithography (SLA), which seem to be gaining ground constantly in the tissue engineering field.

With the use of the methods of tissue engineering and the tools it employs, a digital modelling of an implant that restores the cranial bone is created. The procedure begins with the study of the object of interest, which is the human skull, followed by research regarding the conventional methods of restoration and the biomaterials that will be used. From this research, conclusions are drawn regarding the usefulness of the methods of tissue engineering.

For the creation of the model of the implant, a skull of an actual patient was selected, for the best emulation of the method. In the end, the objects created from the application are presented, and particularly a digital one from the restoration implant. Their usefulness and the conclusions of the procedure are discussed briefly.

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List of Abbreviation

3D-P	3 Dimension printing	MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
ABS	Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene	MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
ALM	Additive Layer Manufacturing	NURBS	Non-uniform rational B-spline
AM	Additive Manufacturing	PCL	Polycaprolactone Polycaprolactone
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange	PDLLA	Polylactic acid
BCP	Biphasic Calcium Phosphate	PED	Precision Extruding Deposition
CAD	Computer Aided Design	PEG	Polyethylene glycol
CAD/CAM	Computer-aided technologies	PFF	Fumarate polypropylene
CATE	Career and Technology Education	PLGA	Polylactic-co-glycolic acid
CNC	Computer Numerical Control	PMMA	Polymethyl Methacrylate
CP	Cathodic protection	PVA	Polyvinyl alcohol
CPC	Calcium Phosphate Cements	PVC	PolyVinyl Chloride
CSG	Constructive Solid Geometry	QCT	Quantitative Computed Tomography
CT	Computed Tomography	ROI	Region of interest
DCPA	Dimethyl Tetrachloro Terephthalate	RP	Rapid Prototyping
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine	SFF	Solid Freeform Fabrication
ECM	Extracellular matrix	SLA	Stereolithography
FDM	Fused Deposition Modelling	SLM	Selective Laser Melting
FEM	Finite element method	SLS	Selective Laser Sintering
HA	Hydroxylapatite	STEP	Standard for Exchange of Product
HAC	Hydroxyapatite Cement	STL	Stereolithography
HDPE	High-Density Polyethylene	TCP	Tricalcium phosphate
HU	Housfield units	TED	Tenders Electronic Daily
IGES	International Graphics Exchange Standard	TTCP	Tetra Calcium Phosphate

LDM	Low-temperature Deposition Manufacturing	USA	United States of America
LM	Layer Manufacturing	UV	UltraViolet
LOM	Laminated Object Manufacturing-	β -TCP	Tribasic Calcium Phosphate
MIMICS	Materialise's Interactive Medical Image Control System		

Prologue

The procedure for the design and the manufacture of the tissue scaffolds belongs to the technological fields of CAD/CAM. The CAD/CAM part is supported by the study regarding their biomaterial or the combination of biomaterials used in the manufacturing of the scaffold, while the latter is tested for its mechanical attributes before it is used in vivo applications. Accordingly, although their ultimate usage purpose belongs to the scientific field of medicine (biomedicine, regenerative medicine), the procedure they are created with clearly belongs to the field of mechanics, technology, and automation, all of which are described by the term tissue engineering.

The manufacture of the scaffolds is based on the established techniques of rapid prototyping, which create the objects layer by layer. The techniques are usually grouped as 3D Printing in the scientific literature, although the term "3D Printing", in reality, is only one of the many similar methods, and it will be used in this paper in that sense.

Tissue mechanics take a growingly larger part of the applications of regenerative medicine. Tissue engineered scaffolds, manufactured with layer by layer methods, are gaining ground, and are, in fact, successfully applied to patients. Although this success is still new and not an everyday fact, it is important to observe a rising trend with good prospects for the future.

Chapter 1 : Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Paper

The 3D modelling of an object in CAD environment is the stage before its manufacture in rapid prototyping machines. Tissue scaffolds are a unique object form, with a more complex geometry and with high graphic requirements in the CAD environment, and a need for precision in their manufacture, due to their intended use. Internally, they are comprised of pores, periodically arranged in the area, that communicate between them, and are made by biomaterials, which are non-hazardous to the human organism. Next, the biomaterials used in cranioplasty and their attributes are studied. Additionally, the design and the display of the implant for the restoration of the skull bone of the hypothetical patient, is analysed. This model is transformed into STL form to create the prototype models of the skull and the implant with rapid prototyping technology. Lastly, the resulting conclusions, and the advantages and the disadvantages of 3D printers, in comparison with the traditional ways of manufacturing that was formerly used, are being discussed.

1.2 Literature Review

In order to establish a theoretical background for this paper, a plethora of publications of scientific teams from universities from many countries was studied, that engage in the same subject. Most of them regard the selection and the testing of biomaterials, observations on the development of organic cultivation in the manufactured scaffolds and studies on their mechanical resistance. The manufacturing, and particularly the designing part, which are of immediate interest in this post-graduate paper, seems to have been studied less.

More precisely, the different approach to the design of tissue scaffold is based on the publication (Starly et al., 2006) . They implemented a "periphrastric" method of scaffold designing, without full modelling in a CAD environment, but filling each of its layers with geometrical patterns and calculating the points that define the borders of each layer.

Regarding the unit cells and their propagation, significant work has been done (Cheah et al., 2003, Díaz Lantada et al., 2016, Wettergreen et al., 2005). They worked on the selection of the appropriate geometry a unit cell could have, and referred to the parameters that should be taken into consideration during the tissue scaffold designing. D. Yoo's (2012) publication regarding the use of more complex unit cells is also interesting . Lastly,

worthy of mention, the rapid prototyping methods that were used for the manufacturing of scaffolds, and to the potential and the limitations of each one (Hutmacher, 2001, Zhou and Wu, 2016).

3D Printers and the need for their manufacture

To turn an idea into a project and then into an object is a complex process, commonly known as production. The transition from the virtual world of design into the natural world of objects previously required workers and technicians who combined experience, skills and knowledge and used the appropriate tools in order to accomplish their goal of giving shape and tangibility to the project. During the last three decades, automated systems based on robotics technology progressively took over the operations above in numerous areas of production. The manufacture of the three-dimensional printer is a completely new stage in the development of automation. Three-dimensional printers provide a direct transition from the digital design or model to the natural, three-dimensional object. These printers use digital files extracted from a physical object that has been scanned, or developed by a mechanic in order to print the object in three dimensions (Balistreri et al., 2015).

The development of 3D printing

We can presume that the concept of three-dimensional printing was conceived in 1976 when the first inkjet printer was manufactured. The first 3D printer was built in 1984 by Charles Hull of "3d Systems". Charles Hull was the inventor of stereolithography, a printing process that results in the printing of three-dimensional objects from digital data.

In 1992, the first stereolithography engine was produced by 3d Systems. This machine consisted of a UV laser, which solidifies the polymer, and thus manufactures a complex structure with successive layers of coatings. In 1999, the first organ cultivated in a lab was set up. Young patients are subjected to an extension of the bladder with the use of a scaffold that has been printed in three-dimensions and has been coated with their cells. This technology was developed by scientists at the Wake Forest Institute for Regenerative Medicine and paved the way for the development of other strategies for three-dimensional organ printing. Since the patient's cells are used, the risk of rejection by the body is minimal to none. Then, in 2002, they built a functioning kidney. This kidney which had the ability to both filter blood, and produce diluted urine, in animals. This invention was instrumental in conducting research at the Wake Forest Institute regarding the printing of

organs and tissues. In 2012, a 3D printed lower jaw was implanted for the first time, to an elderly woman who suffered from a chronic infection of the bone. This technology is being researched to promote the growth of new bone tissue (Beaman, 2015).

Below certain, equally important events in the development of the three-dimensional printer are mentioned. In 2005, Dr. Andrian Bowyer took the initiative for collaboration for the manufacture of the three-dimensional printer, which could print most of its parts. In 2008, an independent additive member, specifically a leg with all its parts was printed, with no requirement for any assemblage. Thus, we have the first person who walks with a three-dimensional printed leg. In 2009; Maker Bot Snowberries introduced the first three-dimensional printers available for sale. In 2011, the first 3D printed car was produced. Friendly towards the environment; it is designed to be fuel-efficient, and cost-effective. Also in 2011, the first three-dimensional printed robotic airplane was manufactured (Bowyer, 2014).

Applications in Biomedicine

3D printing technology is being used in a continuously growing number of medical applications. Trials and prints of structures of cartilages for transplants in joints and cardiac valves have already begun, with the use of compatible materials. Apart from the printing of structural organs, like bones and cartilage from compatible materials, three-dimensional reproduction/printing of vital organs has also been achieved. The potential of printed vital organ transplants is still on a research level. The biological printer Novogen has already been manufactured, and can print three-dimensional cellular tissue, almost identical to the one the human body creates naturally. This "bio-print" allows the creation of identical and three-dimensional human tissue exclusively from living cells, whose compatibility with those of the potential recipient of the implant is checked, naturally. The ultimate objective is the creation of individualized organs for each patient with 'bio-print. "To date, the diagnosis of the need of a vital organ transplant equalled certain death for the patient in the majority of occasions, since, even if a compatible organ from a suitable donor was found, the possibility of rejection from the patient's body was quite large. Therefore, the development of bio-printers will result in significant breakthroughs in the medical field (Winkless, 2015).

In 2007, Organovo was founded, one of the first companies that tried to print organic structures. Currently, Organovo uses samples of liver tissue to research new medicines.

In that way, companies hope to develop a functioning liver shortly. (Chua and Yeong, 2010).

While there is a huge gap between the complexity of printing a plastic figure and an organ, the process is quite similar. The machines used have cassettes and nozzles that sprayed ink (biological ink in this occasion) from layer to layer on a platform. However, there are some basic differences.

We already know that most organs are similar, but in order to study them, scientists must run MRI and CT scans on the patient. Then, they have to run the results through computer software to create a diagram that will act as the guide regarding the way cells are placed on each layer.

Instead of plastic or PVC metal, bio-printers use human cells in every organ they print. From the cells of an actual organ, printers could use the stem cells, materials like a polymer combine called salt of alginic acid and other substitutes that the human body would not reject. In 2012, for example, a 3D printed titanium chin was implanted in an 83-year-old woman, and a man in the USA reacquired his cerebral functions with the help of a three-dimensional skull, in 2013.

As soon as the sample is printed, it has to go into the incubator for the cells to start functioning as a real organ. This is the key issue and the main reason that organ creation devices are not manufactured in hospitals (Hornick, 2016).

According to Jeong and Atala (2015), it is a combination of various issues. The fundamental issue is the use of materials that are utilized in the creation of body members, and then their sufficient development outside of the body. Thus, an organ that was created in a 3D printer could be placed in the patient's body. As we mentioned, the actual organs are complex, and precisely because printed cells are used to create substitute organs, it may mean that they would not function as they were supposed to.

Apart from the issues in the effort to make the cells of a 3D printed organ to function exactly like their natural counterparts, scientists find it equally difficult to create blood vessels needed for arteries, veins and capillary vessels that deliver nutritious substances to the whole organism.

Cranioplasty

From discoveries made, it is known that cranioplasties were being done using plaques made from gold or silver, as substitutes of skull bones. The first transplant of bone tissue from a dog was used in 1670, and the recovery was successful. The number of cranioplasties was increased during the 19th and the 20th century due to war injuries. During this period, the available materials were carbon polymers, phosphate alloplastic, metallic and biological implants. Nowadays, there is much research towards the ideal materials that can be incorporated into bones for plastic surgery and neurosurgery. It is expected that these materials will achieve the surgical and cosmetic goals of both patient and doctors, which were difficult to achieve, to date, with the present methods and transplant materials (Carson et al., 2014).

Figure 1-1 Fractures in the skull

Cranioplasties were performed chiefly to correct a defect in the skull. The majority of skull defects occur due to accidents or abuses (Figure 1.1). The cases requiring cranioplasty are increasing since the victims of accidents receive better treatment. The impact of a strong outer force in the skull can shatter the bone and create a gap of irregular shape. This kind of injury is difficult to treat since the broken bone remains in the cerebral cortex or because the available transplant materials are inadequate to restore a complex and irregular defect. In these cases, the extraction of the defect bone and its replacement with an implant are necessary. Some of the cases also requiring extraction of skull bone are:

- Bone restoration after an operation for the removing of a cancerous brain tumor or of a cancerous brain tumor that has affected the skull tissue.
- Development of a postoperative infection on a patient that has already been subjected to craniectomy

- Decompressive craniectomy: relieving the brain from an oedema (brain hemorrhaging, brain injury). It requires the removal of much bone area. In extreme cases, two areas of the skull are removed.
- Congenital defects that develop dissymmetry and create cosmetic issues

The cases requiring cranioplasty are mainly associated with the size and the location of the injury. Gaps larger than 6cm² certainly require cranioplasty. Additionally, large gaps are occasionally cosmetically unsightly and very dangerous for the exposed brain. A gap in the bone can injure the nervous system and cause a significant neurological issue. Furthermore, psychosocial issues can occur on the individual due to the disfigurement caused by a large gap in the skull bone. The areas of the skull that have the most cosmetic requirements are the front vault, including the frontal bone and the bones around the eye sockets. The restoration of smaller gaps usually occurs for cosmetic reasons. Small gaps do not threaten the brain with injury and are not harmful (Dujovny et al., 1997).

The human skull

The skull is the bony structure of the head that consists of the area surrounding the brain (neurocranium) and the facial skeleton (viscerocranium). It has various functions including the residence and the protection of the brain, the residence of some sensory organs, providing connection points of the brain muscles with the ones in the neck, the formation of the first parts of the digestive and respiratory routes (Figure 1.2) (Sutradhar et al., 2016).

Figure 1-2 Skull Bones – Neurocranium and Viscerocranium

Neurocranium

The human neurocranium consists of six broad, concave bones: the frontal and the nasal are single, the temporal and the zygomatic, double. In the base of the skull, there are the sphenoid and the ethmoid bone, which are characterized by airway cavities. The bones are connected with fibulae, inflexible joints that allow very limited movement. The upper part of the brain cranium is the vault, the lower the base, which is subdivided into three fossae: the anterior, middle, and posterior where the cerebellum resides. Through the base of the skull and the various channels and branches, nerves and blood vessels pass through. In the temporal bone resides the hearing organ. The shapes and sizes of the neurocranium differ: the girth of the skull can be from 52 to 64 cm, the width 12-15 cm and the length 15-18 cm. At birth, the bones of the neurocranium are not yet co-ossified, and there are obvious sutures between the bones referred as fontanelles. The co-ossification is completed in two years. The fontanelles are then named sutures (Dimopoulos et al., 2007, Sutradhar et al., 2016).

The future of 3D printed organs

A team from the University of Mireille, on the other hand, successfully printed cardiac valves and small veins in April, with the hope of creating a functional heart using the cells of one patient, in the future. Cornell researchers created a fake ear from live cells and injectable gel. According to Jeong and Atala (2015), however, roughly 90% of the patients on transplant waiting list require kidneys. Perhaps it is this type of demand that

led a team of Chinese scientists to develop small, printed functioning kidneys, which, unfortunately, have a lifespan of just four months. Atala himself is searching for ways to create a kidney with 3D printing; he has even presented a non-functioning model during his TED speech. During this presentation, the surgeon shared ways that could assist the technology to mature. He spoke of a future where scanners could examine and assess the injuries of patients and then print directly in their body. Since we have not reached that point yet, bio-printed tissue and organs are transferred to labs and medical schools, along with perfect samples, which can then be transplanted into the bodies of patients on the waiting list.

1.3 Structure of the thesis.

For the better organisation and flow of the thesis, the six chapters were grouped in such way, so that they include a total picture of the process of the implant design for the restoration of skull bone. The implementation proposed in this thesis belongs to the part of the process and is analysed in detail, after giving the necessary theoretical background to the reader.

- In the first chapter, the aim of work is explained and a general picture of the literature review that the work is based on, is given.
- The second chapter introduces the reader to the basics of tissue engineering, providing a clear vision of the purpose served by scaffolds in tissue growth. Here data on the biological requirements and requirements of transport in tissue engineering is also presented.
- The third chapter describes the procedure for the production of tissue scaffolds with five basic methods of rapid prototyping and the process described in detail in each case. Furthermore, reference is now made to Bio-CAD modelling and how the CAD data is transferred to the RP machine. Finally, this chapter gives information for cranioplasty and also the structure of the human skull.
- The fourth chapter refers to the biomaterials used in cranioplasty and is divided into categories for better reader understanding.
- Throughout the fifth chapter the design process for an implant for the restoration of skull bone is described. This chapter begins with the collection of medical data by computer tomography and continues with the introduction to imaging software and afterwards to use in their treatment. Finally, it creates the model in STL which

is sent to the rapid prototyping machinery type FDM to complete the 3d printing construction.

- The sixth and final chapter concludes the work and deals with the advantages and disadvantages of 3d bio printing compared to traditional construction methods used at the moment

Chapter 2 : Tissue Engineering and Tissue Engineered Scaffolds

2.1 Tissue Engineering

Tissue Engineering is the combination of the use engineering, cells, material methods and of appropriate biochemical and physicochemical factors. Its purpose is the improvement or the substitution of biological functions. Although at one point, it was considered as a branch of biomaterials, nowadays it has evolved regarding its importance and is regarded as an autonomous field. Most definitions of tissue engineering cover a broad spectrum of applications. In fact, however, the term is closely connected with applications that correct or substitute whole tissues, such as bones, cartilages, cysts, skin and muscles. Frequently, the tissues involved must have specific structural and mechanical properties in order to function properly.

A usually applied definition of tissue engineering, is "understanding the principles of tissue growth, and applying this to produce functional replacement tissue for clinical use."(MacArthur and Oreffo, 2005).

The tissue engineering principle is based on the fact that the cells can be isolated from a patient, to expand through cultivation and to be implanted in a tissue scaffold developed from a biomaterial, in order to for the new issue to be shaped according to the 3D scaffold's form "Figure 2-1". The scaffold plays a major role in the procedure's success since it is its artificial *extracellular matrix* (ECM). It should offer the optimum micro-environment to the cells, in order to attach and to regenerate the failed tissue. The procedure occurs in vitro. Then, the engineered tissue can be transplanted to the same patient as a tissue substitute.

The blood vessels are developed inside this new tissue; the scaffold is destroyed, and the new, complete tissue connects to the surrounding tissue.

Figure 2-1 Tissue Engineering Principle. Source: [Laboratory for Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine, University of Tel Aviv]

The success of the recreation of tissues depends, to a large degree, on the scaffold's ability for structural formation and its bioactivity with the implanted cells. The scaffolds comprise of structural elements such as fibers, pores, and membranes, which can be ordered according to random, fractional or periodical principles and can also be manufactured using engineering approaches. The optimal structural and nutritional conditions are ensured when an already existing, biologically structured tissue is used as a template, as the structure of the scaffold can be designed according to it. For that purpose, significant progress has been made in tissue engineering, in biomaterial science, and in bioengineering, in the optimization of the integration and function of the tissues and also in the design, the configuration and the manufacture of tissue scaffold.

Among the biggest challenges tissue engineering is facing nowadays, is the demand for increasingly advanced functionality and engineering stability in the lab tissues that are meant for transplantation. The eventual development of real replacements of organs and human parts and the continuous success of tissue engineering will be achieved through the convergence of engineering and the progress of the research on tissues, on scaffolds, on growth factors, on stem cells, on the developmental biology, material science, and bioinformatics.

2.2 Purpose of Tissue Engineering

The injury or the failure of an organ or tissue is one of the most painful, but most common cases medicine must face. Furthermore, the treatment is time-consuming, costly and again painful. The field of tissue engineering is the step towards the decrease in deaths, disability, and disorders that occur due to an irreversible injury of a vital organ. The demand for tissue development is showcased through the elements of the previous paragraph. At the beginning of the 1990's, artificial skin was developed for the first time, to be used in cases of burns, followed by the manufacture of cartilage.

The main purpose of tissue engineering is to recreate the structure of the tissues through the combination of biopolymers and biological components such as growth factors and cells, in order to create a proper environment for the development of tissue with identical attributes to the natural one. The biological components are placed on scaffolds (matrices) of biopolymers with a large number of large-sized pores and with the determined proper environmental conditions, their growth is encouraged. The scaffold is implanted in the body where the issue should be located, and the tissue is recreated and connected with the environment while a simultaneous decomposition of the extra-cellular matrix occurs.

The tissue scaffolds must be designed and manufactured to certain specifications. Mechanical, geometrical, biological and transportational specifications must be met for the scaffold to be able to allow the adhesion of cells on its layers, to help their growth and to facilitate their communication and the exchange of components with the environment (Gómez et al.).

2.3 Issues with Tissue Engineering

While there are many applications of tissue engineering, the success in the implantation of scaffolds and the perfect growth of the tissue are not guaranteed at all times. This fact occurs due to a series of obstacles that, unavoidably, coexist with tissue regeneration strategies.

The organism's rejection of the developed cells is not always manageable and the complex geometrical structures existing on natural tissues cannot always be designed and manufactured accurately from the contemporary CAD/CAM systems. These are the biggest obstacles the field of tissue engineering is forced to overcome.

2.4 Possible risks for the human organism

Until now, no one has applied tissue engineering to fully regenerate a tissue, which does not have the capacity of automatic regeneration. Many examples in this direction can be presented, chiefly, in the field of bone restructure.

The model of the skin is distinct proof of tissue engineering's incapability to achieve the purpose mentioned above. The skin developed through tissue engineering in order to restore patients with burns does not have hair or gland structure. Its architecture is close but not identical to the regular mesodermic layer of human skin.

Until now, experience has shown that the full regeneration of tissue may not be necessary, in order to achieve a meaningful clinical result, as, for example, the relief from pain, and the restoration of function or aesthetics.

As in every case where science applies to medical and other matters, and in the case of tissue engineering, it is highly possible that the results from its application can be everything but beneficial for the human organism. Thus, special attention must be given, so as the solution of tissue engineering does not cause more problems than the ones it is trying to solve.

In particular, these risks exist:

- The collection of tissues in order to separate the cells, constitutes high risk to the surrounding tissues and the area of the providing tissue, causing possible degeneration.
- Some implants accelerate the collapse of the surrounding tissues

2.5 Potential of Prospects of Tissue Engineering

In a relatively new field, as is tissue engineering, it is useful to examine its potential. Due to its direct connection to human health, the interest is quite significant, even more since some successful in vivo scaffold transplantations have been achieved.

The most significant prospect is the creation of a new philosophy for a cure and the treatment of diseases, chiefly those impossible to cure with contemporary methods. The plethora of diseases adds another challenge to the field of tissue engineering and makes

it clear that a universal strategy can be developed in order to treat them. On the contrary, we are constantly dealing with individual cases that demand different treatment each time.

2.6 Tissue Scaffolds

The tissue scaffold is the base that will host the cell cultivation and, either in the biomimetic environment (in vitro), or directly implanted in the patient (in vivo), will contribute to the regeneration and the shaping of the new tissue. It is a porous manufacture "Figure 2-2", consisting of one or more unit geometrical structures-unit cells, periodically set in the area "Figure 2-3". Regarding the design of tissue scaffolds, "pore" is defined as the empty area surrounded by the unit cell and varies from tens of micrometers up to a few micrometers. Apart from the support, the scaffold's decomposition must result in non-toxic products, with the ulterior purpose of its full absorption by the organism. This requires the exclusive use of bio-compatible and biodegradable material with proper attributes for the manufacture of the scaffold. Regarding the biomaterials, an extensive analysis will follow.

Figure 2-2 Tissue Scaffold a) Cylindrical model, b) bone model

Figure 2-3 Unit Cell for the bone model

The design and manufacture of the scaffold is a complex procedure that demands research. The first obstacles occur during their design, which takes place in a 3D CAD environment. Due to the complexity of the manufacturing process, designing them with conventional means often proves difficult and sometimes completely unachievable. Thus, it must be approached in a different way. The detailed exterior geometry of cartilage or the complex interior patterns of cancellous bone are hard challenges due to the limitations of contemporary CAD software. The manufactured scaffold must meet certain requirements, which are examined separately.

2.6.1 Requirements of mechanical durability

Every tissue of the human body performs unique functions and thus has its own demands for levels of mechanical durability. Bone, for example, must ensure the required rigidity in order to protect the soft tissues it surrounds, function as a store room for trace elements, and transport the forces that move the skeleton. Additionally, it must endure the different loads it receives and, at the same time, to support the regeneration of tissue.

The mechanical specifications of the scaffold are crucial to the stability of the manufacture. The surface tension, the void fraction, and the scaffold's stiffness measure play an important part and affect its mechanical attributes considerably. This is due to the forces applied from the continuously growing biological elements of the tissue inside the scaffold. A possible fault would be disastrous for the creation of tissue, affecting the whole scaffold.

The load-bearing conditions of bone are limited to a particular range during the everyday activities of the musculoskeletal system. The scaffold must play a double role: On the one hand it must retain its geometry without failing under the load it receives and on the contrary, as it decomposes, it must transport the load to the bone. The transplant has a

therapeutic role. As it gradually transfers the load it receives to the bone, it triggers the development of biological elements, which will gradually relieve the traumatized area.

2.6.2 Biological requirements

One of the most important factors in the manufacturing of the 3D tissue scaffold is its manufacturing material. The attributes of the material related its bio-compatibility and its biodegradability play an important part in the tissues that will be regenerated. Bio-compatibility refers to the organism's lack of reaction to the implant and, at the same time, the possession of the proper chemical properties on the surface, which will help the attachment and development of the cells. The term biodegradability refers to the decomposition of the material to non-toxic products that will be absorbed or removed from the organism, leaving behind only the healthy tissue.

Other crucial parameters are cell adhesion and distribution. The former refers to the cells' ability to adapt to their environment and to connect with the surrounding structures. Their connection is a biological reaction and is achieved through adhesive substances on to the scaffold's surface. Furthermore, it has been proven that the surface's attributes play an important role in the degree of cell adhesion (Salerno et al., 2015). On the contrary, the scaffold's connection to its environment is mostly based on geometrical and topological attributes, as is the relationship angle and the degree of its rigidity. Lastly, another interesting biological attribute is the scaffold's ability to receive additional substances, which help and accelerate the development of tissue.

2.6.3 Transport requirements

In tissue engineering, the term "transport" refers to the procedure during which the nutritious components of the cells' function move in the interior of the scaffold, with the ability to reach every interior surface. These components keep the cells healthy. Their transport should be achieved easily both inside and outside the scaffold. Molecules of glucose, oxygen, and other chemical components should be able to easily reach the interior of the manufacture. Inadequate transportation or transport of a lesser amount of components than those required ends in cell necrosis. On the contrary, the metabolism's products (carbon dioxide) and other byproducts should be transported outside the scaffold. Any inability to dispose of them raises the acidity in the environment, leading, once more, to cell necrosis. Both of the above situations contribute to the appearance of a

phenomenon known in scientific literature as shell effect, which has been observed in static cultivations.

The nutritional components and the waste products are grouped due to the transport's phenomena of dissemination and flow. Through the dissemination, all components are homogenized in a joint environment, due to their random movement. Flow, on the other hand, intensifies the phenomenon.

The continuation of the transport of nutritional components inside and outside of the scaffold is a crucial factor in its manufacture. Since a tissue scaffold consists of unit geometrical structures that are repeated on the site, its design should ensure the communication between them. Another factor that can affect the diffusion of nutritious components in the scaffold is the cell's growth, by itself. Their multiplication can reach such a degree that it will obstruct the transport routes, interrupting the communication of the interior surfaces with the environment, resulting in cell necrosis.

The manufacture of a diffusion network is a new approach to the above issue. The network orientates and directs the necessary components to the scaffold's interior, but is manufactured from a material that does not allow the attachment of cells and thus, the diffusion will never be interrupted from the inside due to interference from another material. Hydrogels are the materials used towards that purpose.

2.7 Mechanical strength of 3D scaffolds

The scaffold must ensure the required mechanical strength during the implantation and the gradual regeneration of tissue. Especially in cases where significant amounts of pressure are developed due to weight (cartilages, bones), the implant must support the development of tissue, as it disintegrates and is absorbed by the organism. Its stability depends on factors such as elasticity, durability, and its chemical degradation.

The mechanical attributes of the scaffold must be as similar as possible to the skeleton's part they are replacing. Those include resistance to pressure, torsion, and bending tendencies. The attribute of resistance to pressure is more associated with cancellous bones while that of elasticity with cortical bones. The elasticity factor and the pressure developed depend on a series of factors.

- The scaffold's composition and the density of pore interconnection inside the scaffold's network

- The relative density. The elasticity factor is very sensitive to changes in relative density. It is worth mentioning that small alterations to the scaffolds porous can bring significant changes to the relative density. The elasticity factor alters significantly according to the density's square ρ^2 .
- The geometry of the scaffold is a unit cell. The elasticity factor's dependence on geometry is relatively small. (Μαυρίδη and Mavridi, 2007)

The monitoring of the mechanical strength is achieved through the finite element method (FEM). FEM is a numerical technique for finding approximate solutions to boundary value problems for partial differential equations, when the analytical solution of the equation is not possible, where the strains and the geometric figures are unusual

Chapter 3 : Manufacturing of Scaffold Tissue

3.1 Manufacturing of scaffolds with Rapid Prototyping

A well-known and effective way of scaffold tissue manufacturing is achieved through the methods of Freeform Fabrication (SFF) or Rapid Prototyping (RP). Through these techniques, 3D models are manufactured in layers. The procedure is: the material is picked for processing in powder form, in liquid resin form or filament form, according to each RP method. A fragile layer of material, in the order magnitude of μm , is placed on the processing surface and then melts or solidifies. The procedure is repeated for each layer, which is joined with the previous one, creating a solid object. The data for the shaping of each layer is received from the CAD software used. The 2D layer is the intersection between the umpteenth surface and the CAD model. After they are extracted in the proper format, they are fed to the RP machine, for the scaffold to be developed in layers.

Due to the procedure above, those methods appear in scientific literature as Additive Manufacturing (AM), Layer Manufacturing (LM) and Additive Layer Manufacturing (ALM). The development in layers gives a number of capabilities in controlling the manufacturing of complex structures, and this is the reason why it is being used in biomedicine since 2000. The automation of the procedure, the frequently needed close inspection of the mechanical and the geometric attributes, such as the pore's size and the interconnection between them have established the RP methods in the field of tissue engineering. Furthermore, the communication between RP machines and MRI scanners provides the capability to manufacture personalized scaffolds, compatible in size and form with each patient individually (Hutmacher et al., 2004).

The various methods of layer-development differ among them in the way they shape the scaffold. Their differences will be explained below.

3.1.1 Stereolithography (SLA)

Stereolithography is one of the first rapid prototyping techniques. The first SLA machine is put on the market in 1988 by 3D Systems Inc. The method is based on the polymerization of a photopolymerization resin caused by the energy of electromagnetic radiation, as it falls on its surface. The photopolymerization resins are mixtures of monomers of low molecular weight, capable of reacting with and shaping solid polymers

when they receive radiation of a specific wavelength. They are placed inside a vat, directly underneath the scanning area, where a system of elevation/sinking of the manufactured unit exists, in order to ensure that the radiation is falling in the liquid resin for every new layer. «Figure 3-1.»

There are two basic alternatives in the implementation of stereolithography systems. The first one is based on an ultraviolet laser beam, which, after being mirrored on a reflector, falls on the surface of the material and solidifies it, point by point. The second uses whole images, which are displayed and then mirrored on the reflector, polymerizing the entire layer of resin placed on the surface simultaneously (Zhou and Wu, 2016).

The ultraviolet beam falls on a mirror, which is guided by a computer, and directs it towards relative point $P(x,y)$ which is read from the loaded CAD file for the particular layer. When it falls on the surface of the material, a layer of plastic is created due to polymerization, upon the surface and, marginally, beneath it. The procedure is repeated for the layers of the processing object until it takes its final shape. Next, the object solidifies inside ultraviolet furnaces, while an extra conditioning corrects random anomalies that may occur on the surface. The analysis of the process depends on the pace of the sinking mechanism of the SLA platform and on the diameter of the laser beam and, where the successive layer processing is being done. A contemporary SLA machine can have a laser diameter of 80-250 μm and can achieve layer thickness up to 1.3 μm .

Figure 3-1 SLA machine setting.

The use of stereolithography in the field of tissue engineering is focused on the manufacturing of scaffolds for educational uses and less on in vivo applications. On the one hand, due to the required post-processing, the object is condensed, affecting the desired resolution. Thus, we have a predetermined fault, since post processing is necessary for the solidification of the scaffold. On the other hand, as the size decreases and the complexity of the parts that have to be formulated increase the outcome becomes distorted. This occurs due to the absorption and topical release of the beam on the liquid (Hutmacher et al., 2004).

The answer to the above issue is the use of a relatively new technique called Microstereolithography (µSL). The function principals are similar to the ones of SLA, except the fact that in order to achieve greater resolution, the laser beam targets with greater accuracy on the photopolymerization liquid, decreasing its diameter in a few µm. Solidified layers, with 1-10 µm thickness, are created in that fashion (Papazetis and Vosniakos, 2016).

The materials selected for the manufacturing of scaffolds must be bio-compatible, biodegradable and to ensure mechanical strength. The range of photopolymerization objects that fulfill the above requirements is not particularly large, another obstacle for the use of stereolithography in tissue engineering applications. Some of them are polyethylene glycol (PEG), methacrylate polyethylene glycol, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), modified polysaccharides, methacrylate dextran, fumarate polypropylene (PFF) and the polylactic acid (PDLLA) (Hollister, 2011, Langer and Vacanti, 2016, Papazetis and Vosniakos, 2016).

3.1.2 Selective Laser Sintering (SLS)

SLS rapid prototyping method was developed by Carl Deckard and Joe Beaman in 1985 at the University of Austin, in Texas. It is also based on the use of the laser beam as a medium for modulation. It usually uses a carbon dioxide (CO₂) laser, which creates an ultraviolet radiation beam with a wavelength between 9.4 and 10.6 µm. The material here is in powder form, which is evenly applied to the surface with the assistance of a roller. Next, the laser beam scans the points according to the data it reads from the loaded file for every layer. The transported heat from the laser increases the temperature of the material above the point of glass transition (T_g), forcing the specks of powder to create an aggregate locally and, consequently, one or more solidified areas in the layer. "Figure 3-2." (Tan et al., 2005).

Figure 3-2 SLS machine setting..

The typical size of the specks is 0.1-0.15 mm, up to a few μm . When the process is finished on the layer or when it submerges with the help of a moving platform, across the vertical axis Z, fresh powder is applied on the surface of the machine, burying the previous layer. The fusion procedure is repeated, and every new layer connects with the previous, creating a homogenous mass. At the end of the procedure, the object can be retrieved from the chamber, while further processing can be implemented if deemed necessary.

The typical layer a contemporary SLS machine can achieve ranges from 80 to 200 μm and the power of the laser can reach up to 70W. The manufacturing of tissue scaffolds in SLS machines can be achieved with many biocompatible materials in the group of polymers or ceramics. Due to the regular distribution of the laser beam that transmits freely in the environment, the creation of angular parts in SLS machines is difficult. This dissipation creates unwanted joints of material particles, which affects the quality of the manufacturing scaffold creating harsh surfaces. The harshness in the interior can cause material entrapment. The solution for the issues above comes from the continuous decrease of the diameter of the laser beam and the size of the particles of the material used. The trapped material can be removed from the interior of the porous scaffold with ultrasound vibrations, compressed air, and solvents (Zhou and Wu, 2016).

One of the most usual materials used for the manufacturing of scaffolds in SLS is polycaprolactone (PCL). It is a bioabsorbable and biodegradable polyester, which has a

very low melting point at 55°C. It can be used in the applications for bone and cartilage regeneration, with high prospects. Specifically, PCL scaffolds, manufactured with the SLS method, can fully cover the requirements of the skeletal tissue (Mazzoli et al., 2015). They are not limited by any the possible increased complexity of the anatomy in some applications. The mechanical attributes of the tissue engineered scaffolds can be calculated and thus, experimental tests are not necessary.

Lee was the first to manufacture a scaffold from a ceramic material with the SLS method (Sansalone et al., 2016). Particularly, calcium phosphate was used for the 3D scaffold, for the purpose of regenerating part of the lower jaw in a dog. The evaluation showed that the scaffold was bio-compatible, and the part of the bone was developed smoothly.

The laser fusion method (SLS) allows the use of synthetic, in addition to the main materials used. In that fashion, there are cases where the polycaprolactone (PCL) is mixed with Hydroxylapatite (HA), which is a calcium-phosphorous mineral, and calcium phosphate. Tissue scaffold made from polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and Hydroxylapatite (HA) "Figure 3-3."

Figure 3-3 Scaffolds manufactured in SLS. A) PHBV, B) CaP/PHBV, C) PLLA, D) CHAp/PLLA.

Lastly, it is worth noting the introduction of Selective Laser Melting (SLM) in the field of tissue engineering. It is a technique identical to SLS, with the only difference being the higher power laser needed for the melting of the materials. The materials used are mainly stainless steel, alloys of cobalt-chromium (Co-Cr) and titanium (Ti). The use of SLM is limited to the manufacturing of additional implants with these materials. However, there

have been attempts to manufacture scaffolds from biodegradable materials like tribasic calcium phosphate (β -TCP) and polylactic acid (PDLA) with the favourable potential of shaping complex pores.

3.1.3 Three Dimensional Printing (3DP)

Three Dimensional Printing technology was developed at MIT and has been widely researched regarding its efficiency in the manufacturing of scaffolds for biological regeneration. It is the first of the methods of additive manufacturing (AM) that was used in the field of tissue engineering.

The principals of operation are based on ink-jet technology. The 3D printer has a nozzle, which applies binder solution on the material that has been spread. The processing material is in powder form, as in the case of SLS, with a particle size of 80-250 μm . In contrast to the laser fusion method, the solution glues the particles together without them having melted previously. From then on, the procedure is repeated with the next layer of material being spread on the machine's platform and is straightened with the help of a roller "Figure 3-4." The new layer that is bonded will connect with the previous one, resulting, in the end, in a new solid piece.

Figure 3-4 3D Printing machine configuration.

The resolution of 3D printers is limited by the diameter of the nozzle, affecting the minimum feature that is possible to be processed in such a machine. Additionally, the layer's thickness depends on the material's particle size. The material's powder form applies a final limitation to the cases where the objects are not solid but have pores in

their interior. The difficulty that arises has to do with the particles that are trapped inside the pores, which are difficult to remove in the object's post processing. The problem is common in both 3D printers and SLS machines. Some organic solvents used as welding mediums for the particles have been proven harmful for the human organism (Zhou and Wu, 2016). Such solvents are chloroform and chloride methacrylate. Even after special processing for the removal of unwanted binder substances from the scaffold, its complete elimination is impossible.

According to Lam et al.(2002) research, natural biopolymers (dextran, gelatin) were used as main ingredients in the manufacturing of scaffolds and distilled water was used as the adhesive substance. On the one hand, it resolved the issue with the use of organic solvents. On the contrary, it produced a water soluble scaffold, in need of extended processing in order to become insoluble in water.

The advantage of 3D printing is the wide choice of manufacturing materials. Various materials have been used either in studies, single or in combination with others. Detsch et al. (2010) manufactured scaffolds from hydroxylapatite, from tribasic calcium phosphate (β -TCP) and a mixture of biphasic calcium phosphate (BCP) with HA of about 60% by weight. Ge et al. (2009), studied cell development and manufactured TE scaffold from polylactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA). After three weeks, the developed bone was examined for its mechanical strength. The results showed that PLGA scaffolds responded successfully to the requirements of porous, agile and low-density part of the bone (trabecular bone), but showed considerable weaknesses in cases of solid areas of the bone (cortical bone). Other materials used for in vitro research were gypsum (calcium sulfate dihydrate) with a particle size of 10-20 μm , a mixture of TCP with calcium diphosphate and pure titanium. The latter was used in dental applications and showed tensile yield strength of 4,8-13,2 GPa, which covers the tensile yield strength of the natural bone (Eufinger et al., 2005).

A variant of the 3D Printing method is the 3D phase change inkjet printer. In this case, there are two separate nozzles. From the first, thermoplastic material emerges and from the second a material with candle-like texture and a low melting point (50-90°C). These are spread on the work platform and are fused topically due to the heat transmission, thus shaping each layer of the object under construction.

Figure 3-5 A) Scaffold manufactured from HA B) Detail of the scaffold's interior

3.1.4 Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM)

FDM has a slightly different philosophy than the previous methods. It was developed by S. Scott Crump in 1988 and was commercialized two years later by Stratasys Inc.

FDM's main difference from the SFF methods previously examined is the lack of any object in powder form (SLS, 3DP) or retinoids (SLA), spread on the working platform or channeled in a vat. The material processed on an FDM machine is thermoplastic, in fibrous form, wrapped around a roller. The material's fibers are directed with the assistance of a wheel to the extrusion nozzle. There, the heated head increases the temperature of the thermoplastic material, resulting in its melting. At this point, a resemblance with the 3D Phase Change Inkjet Printing method becomes obvious, which is an alternative to 3DP. The nozzle is directed according to the data read from the loaded file and ejects the material in the form of droplets that solidify immediately. As this is another LM method, FDM machines are provided with a platform moving across the vertical axis. The next layer of processed material will be used as the substrate of the previous one, and thus, it must retain a temperature a little lower than the solidification temperature of the thermoplastic material, in order to achieve unification with the new material "Figure 3-6".

Figure 3-6 FDM machine configuration

The FDM method has been repeatedly tested in the manufacturing of scaffolds with excellent results regarding the exterior geometry of the scaffolds, as we are about to see. It is limited, to a degree, when complex pores must be manufactured in the interior of the scaffold, in comparison with the techniques that process material spread on the working platform. Additionally, the spread material in the SLS and 3Dp techniques ensures support to the part shaped in layers, an advantage that does not apply to FDM method. Lastly, the exclusive use of the thermoplastic material in thread form and the temperature's effect on the material are two more obstacles.

In order to solve the issues with the FDM method, alternative techniques have been developed, always based on the same extrusion-based RP techniques. The first one is called Precision Extruding Deposition (PED) and avoids a large part of the material's preparation when it must be rolled as a thread around the roller (filament preparation). With the PED technique, the material in use is in powder or pellet form. It is provided to the machine directly, as its head is heating and is ejected through the rotary motion of bolts. It is worth noting that this specific method of ejection applies the material on the platform with higher precision (Cho et al., 2016). The second alternative manages to bypass the heat treatment applied to materials during the classic method of ejection. This technique is called Low-temperature Deposition Manufacturing (LDM) and uses multiple nozzles during the modulation, allowing the manufacturing of scaffolds from many materials.

Another alternative to the techniques based on the ejection of material is the Bio-Plotting method. It was developed at the Freiburg Materials Research Centre, in Germany and was commercialized by Envision Technologies GmbH. In this case, a very small needle is used as a nozzle. The material is initially stored in heated cartridges and comes out of the needle in droplet form. A vat with a special solution is placed under the needle's scanning area. The droplet falls in the solution and solidifies through cooling, heating, or due to the chemical reaction between the material and the solution. The use of a solution of equal density with the material is a good way to avoid the need for a supporting structure for the manufactured scaffold.

With the alternative techniques available, the variety of available materials has increased significantly. The team of Hutmacher, Teoh and associates deals systematically with the manufacturing of tissue scaffolds made from PCL and PCL/TCP, with the FDM method. The scaffolds are available commercially from Osteopore. Their application deals with the regeneration of parts of the skull (Hollister, 2011). For the same purpose, Bourell et al. (2010) used polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) with favourable results, establishing its use in biomedicine. Also, the mixture of polymers with calcium phosphate produces a series of desirable biological and mechanical attributes on the scaffolds, while mixtures of PLGA collagen type II (Yen et al., 2009) and polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) have been evaluated as basic ingredients (Chanthakulchan et al., 2015). Mixtures of polylactic glycolic acid with calcium phosphate were used in the manufacture of scaffolds with LDM method, while polycaprolactone, and its mixture with hydroxylapatite, was implemented by Shoretal (2007) with the method of accurate ejection PED. Lastly, Ye et al. (2010) manufactured a scaffold by mixing non-stoichiometric apatite (ns-HA) with PCL, based on the BioPlotting method. The results for ns-HA by weight was a good interconnection among the pores with 400-500 μm size and a maximum porosity of 76%.

3.1.5 Laminated Object Manufacturing– (LOM)

The corresponding technology to the method is the Laminated Object Manufacturing - LOM. In this technology, a laser beam is used in order to trace the outline of each layer. The manufacturing material is inserted with a heated roller to achieve welding with a special temperature sensitive glue. The laser's power is set in order to penetrate up to a depth equal to each layer's thickness. The excess material is cut in rectangular pieces for easier extraction, although it remains for the largest part of the procedure and acts as support. The material sheet is larger than the manufacturing area so as the sheet's edges

remain untouched. This means that when the first layer is completed, and the under substrate is lowered, the roller with the material can proceed with rolling the waste to a second roller until the section is covered with the second sheet. The whole procedure can be repeated. In Figure 3.7, a diagram of the Laminated Object Manufacturing is presented.

Figure 3-7 LOM machine configuration

3.2 Usual method of 3D scaffolds' design

Considering that rapid prototyping methods have been established as the manufacturing method of 3D tissue scaffolds, CAD programs (Computer Aided Design) are the established designing platform.

In tissue engineering, the 3D model of the bone, of the tissue and, generally, of the area we want to regenerate, is received through Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) or Computed Tomography (CT). The image received from the tomography is coded in files of a specific type, which can be processed by CAD software. In the CAD environment, on the other hand, 3D scaffold models are designed, consisting of one or more unit cells that interconnect and are periodically repeated in the area. Next, with Boole operations (conjunction, disjunction, and negation) the model of the 3D scaffold is defined by the exterior geometry of the bone or the tissue that must be developed, and from a pattern of

repeated pores in its interior "Figure 3-8." 3D models are transformed into file formats recognizable by rapid prototyping machines. The STL (Stereolithography) file is one of those forms of the CAD model towards the machine that will manufacture it, but it is not the only one. The rapid prototyping machine slices the model in parallel planes (slicing) in order to manufacture it in layers (layer manufacturing). "Figure 3-9" shows the usual scaffold manufacturing procedure described above.

3.3 Bio-CAD modelling

The depiction of the anatomy of bone, organ, or tissue of the human body has been a significant challenge during the last decades. Great progress, both in software and hardware, has created the conditions for more accuracy in the manufacturing of 3D models in a CAD environment. Science literature refers to this procedure as bio-CAD modelling.

Figure 3-8 Section between a bone part and the 3D scaffold

Figure 3-9 Procedure of the design and manufacturing of 3D scaffolds

From this point on, the manufacturing procedure of 3D scaffolds is initiated, with the data received from medical images. Specifically, medical images that produce a 3D image and provide anatomical and structural data are of value to the field of Tissue Engineering. The most widely known are Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Computed Tomography (CT). Data is provided by matching each essential part of the image with one physical quantity that presents modulation among the tissues, as is the weakening of X-rays in CT and the downward transition of magnetically active material in MRI. In both cases, the patient's exposure to ionized radiation is demanded.

The advantage of the CT is the higher resolution of the images. MRI, on the other hand, is a great solution regarding the body's tissues. It is capable of differentiating the hard from the soft tissues, even among tissues of similar density. For that reason, CT and MRI can be used to supplement each other, for a complete picture to be displayed, in cases needed.

The images received in the previous stage proceed to the stage of segmentation, during which the area of interest is cut from the general display "Figure 3.10 a". The images are placed one atop the other as slices of a specific thickness. Each slice consists of cubical components that occupy certain volume, voxels "Figure 3.10 b." The vertical placement of the slices creates a 3D image composed of voxels "Figure 3.10 c." The procedure is labourious and requires high computing and processing power since the slices are many

and the organization and management of the provided data is difficult. However, they are within the capabilities of contemporary software.

Figure 3-10 A) Image splitting, b) Voxel, c) 3D voxel model

From then on, data is coded and organized in different ways, for the medical images to become 3D CAD models that can be processed, with their topology factors (solid figures, surfaces, edges) being available. Sun et al. (2005) assessed three different approaches to the subject .

In the first one, they used MedCAD to receive data from the tomographies in STEP (Standard for Exchange of Product), IGES (International Graphics Exchange Standard) or STL (Stereolithography) files. This particular method proved to be fast but met obstacles during cases of complex tissue anatomy.

In the second one, an approach of reverse engineering was used. Initially, the voxels that comprise the 3D image were transformed into point coordinates, which were inserted in the software. For every three points, currently, an individual triangular surface is created. The exterior surface of the model consists of many such triangular surfaces. Unnecessary components are frequently removed from the model, in order to improve its quality and to decrease file size. For the stabilization of the exterior geometry, the exterior surfaces are depicted with b-spline curves (NURBS). The method required the largest processing time among the three, but produced the best and steadiest results "Figure 3-11."

Figure 3-11 CAD model through reverse engineering approach

During the last test, researchers transformed the 3D voxel model into an STL file and then inserted it in the reverse engineering software, in order to improve its exterior surfaces by interpolating NURBS curves. The advantage of this method was the brief implementation time for an, otherwise, mediocre result, particularly due to the nature of STL files.

3.4 Transferring CAD data to the RP machine

When the modelling of the scaffold in the CAD design environment is finished, a method of transferring the geometrical data to the rapid prototyping machine is required. The most common way is the transformation of data to STL (Stereolithography) form. Nowadays, all designing software has an interface for the creation of STL files, because it is an industry standard. However, apart from that, other translators accommodate the connection between CAD and Solid Freeform Fabrication environment.

3.4.1 STL

STL consists of an unclassified list of triangular sides, which represent the exterior surfaces of the solid. There are two types of STL files: ASCII and binary. The latter is more commonly used since it is smaller than ASCII, but non-recognizable by humans. The triangular sides of the STL file are defined by the coordinates X, Y, Z of their three apexes and from the unit vector, perpendicular to the surface of the facet, which shows which side of the layer belongs to the object.

The STL form is a reconstruction of the CAD model with triangular sides, actually an approximation. The precision of the reconstruction depends, to a large degree, on the stability of the tessellation each CAD commercial program includes. This causes corruptions in the manufacture's geometry, which are even more common in cases of complex geometry, such as the tissue scaffolds. Additionally, STL files are, by far, larger than 3D CAD model files, for the given desired precision. This occurs because STL carries much unnecessary information, such as double edges and apexes, as in "Figure 3-12".

In the case of tissue engineered scaffolds, whose exterior surface is shaped based on numerous curves and the pores on their interior require high manufacturing detail, the size of the STL file grows forbiddingly large.

Figure 3-12 Unnecessary information in STL file.

A final disadvantage of the specific format is the time required for the slicing procedure of the 3D model to be processed in the RP machine. However, STL is the simplest way of transferring 3D CAD data to the rapid prototyping machine and the most accurate for specific figures.

During the extraction of the file from commercially available CAD software, the user selects the parameters that define the precision of the image of the 3D model in STL format. The most basic among them is the deviation (in CAD software it is also called chord height or surface height). It is the maximum deviation an edge of a triangular side of STL can have, compared to the curve that describes the corresponding surface of the CAD model. An increase of tolerance will result in the decrease of the number of triangles that describe the surfaces and thus, smaller file size and faster creation. Evidently, this

will have an impact in the detail and the resolution of the object to be manufactured. On the other hand, the decrease of chord height will create opposite data and thus, objects of higher resolution and detail. In practice, there is no reason for an object's detail to increase after a point. The restriction comes from the attributes of the rapid prototyping machine, specifically resolution and minimum layer thickness". Figure. 3.13" shows the association between the chord height and the technical attributes of the Zcorp printer.

Figure 3-13 Selection of chord height in ZCorp 3D Printer.

3.5 Tissue scaffold design

The procedure of designing biomimetic tissue scaffold is based on CATE and is initiated with the acquiring of images and their processing, initially selecting the tissue's area of interest. Next is the 3D redevelopment of the anatomical structure using reverse engineering (for example Geomagic and MIMICS) and commercially available software of medical reconstruction. The procedures for the manufacture of CAD models result in the scaffolds above. The next step is the identification of the structural attributes of the tissue in order to determine the structural attributes of the scaffold model. Next is the manufacture of scaffold blocks using the CAD environment in structural unit form. Based on geometrical modulation and the proposed materials of the scaffold, the method of finite components is applied, in order to determine the mechanical attributes of the structural units. These attributes are then compared with the mechanical attributes of the tissue to be replaced, with the method of quantitative computer tomography (QCT). The structural units with similar attributes are selected to constitute the scaffold. Then the selected

structural units are appraised according to their interior architecture in relation to appropriate biological objectives. Applying Boolean functions and using the Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG), models of the solids of the structural units are designed, which can acquire the bone's form. When, eventually, the CAD design of the model of the tissue scaffold of the osteitis is completed, begins the procedure of its manufacturing using manufacturing techniques of free form solids.

Chapter 4 : Biomaterials use in cranioplasty

When a synthetic material is placed inside the human body, tissue reacts to the implant in various ways depending on the material's type. The interaction mechanism of the tissues with the material (if there is one) depends on the reaction of the tissue to the implant's surface. Biomedical materials can be separated into two categories depending on the tissue's reaction:

Bioinert: This term refers to any material that, when placed inside the human organism, has minimum interaction with the surrounding tissue. Examples of bioinert materials used in cranioplasty are titanium and high-density polyethylene.

Bioactive: The interaction of natural body tissues - bone and soft tissues, with foreign materials that have been inserted into the body, is known as bioactivity. This insertion sets off a chain of reactions due to time and motion alterations on the surface of the implant. A layer of activated carbonate apatite (CHAp) is created due to an ionic exchange reaction at the interface of the insert and bodily fluids, that is equal to the bone's metallic phase, both chemically and crystallographically. An example of this would be synthetic hydroxyapatites $[Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2]$ (Evans and McGrath, 2015).

Metals are usually inert, ceramics can be inert, active or absorbable, and polymers can be inert or absorbable.

A biomaterial used in cranioplasty as an implant must meet certain, crucial requirements.

Biocompatibility: Biomaterials used in the restoration of skull gaps must be, most of all, biocompatible with the organism that will receive them. This means that the material must not cause inflammatory reactions, must not be cytotoxic, carcinogenic or allergenic. Furthermore, it must not be rejected from the organism, but stay inside it for life.

Mechanical attributes: It is important in cranioplasty, as in every orthopedic operation of bone restoration, to ensure the appropriate mechanical attributes of the biomaterial. These attributes must be as identical as possible to the ones of replaced tissue. Thus, the proper mechanical support is ensured. Mechanical attributes include resistance to pressure, tension, and torsion. The attribute of resistance to pressure is mostly associated with cancellous bone, while elasticity relates to cortical bones.

Sterilization capability: The materials for the implant must be easy to sterilize, to prevent infections. The sterilization method, though, must not collide with the material's biocompatibility or the bioactivity.

Impact Time - Change of Temperature: The material must be able to be placed inside the patient's body in a few minutes to decrease the duration of the whole procedure and the possibility of an infection. Furthermore, the change of the biomaterial's temperature must be limited to a degree that will not allow the necrosis of nearby, healthy tissue (Sun et al., 2005).

The nature and the attributes of the biomaterial used as an implant define its manufacturing method and its placement technique. The success of the implants depends on their proper handling and the proper surgery technique during their placement inside the human body. Implants that do not have a sufficiently, accurate form present difficulties in their insertion and are not safe. Furthermore, the misshaping result can lead to the necrosis of the skull tissue, and infections (Tan et al., 2016).

Biomaterials extensively used as skull bone replacements are Pure Titanium, Polymethacrylic Methyl Ester, Hydroxyapatite and High-Density Polyethylene.

4. 1. Metallic biomaterials

Among the metals used in cranioplasty, the dominant one is titanium (Ti). Titanium is a metallic element that was discovered in 1796. For more than 45 years, it has been used, with great success, as a material for transplants in orthopedics, neurosurgery, dentistry, and in skull prosthetics, due to its durability against mechanical strains. It shows exceptional biocompatibility inside the human body. Pure titanium does not corrode inside the human organism and always retains its chemical stability. It is non-allergenic, non-carcinogenic, and does not cause inflammatory reactions (Fu et al., 2016). It can be manufactured in the proper form and can be compressed, bent, welded, pierced, and burnished. Its chemical attributes remain unchanged during the moulding process (Wehmöller et al., 2004). It retains its form inside the human body. Up to a degree, it allows radiation to pass through it (to the same degree as the bone) and it is biologically inactive. The thickness of titanium skull implants does not exceed 2mm (Eufinger et al., 1995). It has, a relatively, small tensile module, a fact that makes it function similarly to bones. Regarding its density, it is much lower in comparison to other metallic biomaterials, and thus, titanium implants are much lighter than those manufactured from stainless steels

and cobalt-chromium alloys. The human body identifies titanium and its alloys as hosts and tries to isolate them surrounding them with fibrous tissues. However, they do not cause dangerous reactions, and the organism tolerates them. Titanium is easily available and at a reasonable price (Chen et al., 2015, Eufinger et al., 2003, Sun et al., 2005). On Figure 4.1, a 3D digital skull model is depicted, upon which, a photograph of the titanium implant which was designed and manufactured according to the digital model, has been placed.

Figure 4-1 3D digital skull model and titanium implant.

The main disadvantage of titanium transplants is that the organism considers them an alien body, and thus, there is a possibility for the organism to reject them, in the long term. Inside the human organism, titanium implants show irregular thermal conduction. Various patients complained of headaches and annoying pressure after cranioplasty with titanium implants. Furthermore, they are not suggested for young patients, whose skeleton is still under growth (Yeo et al., 2014). Lastly, titanium has the disadvantage that it is difficult to mould, cut, and shape in comparison to other materials, and its processing is quite costly (Dujovny et al., 1997). It is necessary for skull gaps to be restored for the protection of the brain but also for cosmetic reasons. The premade implants not only cover those needs but also help in reducing the duration of the surgical operation and are more efficient in the restoration of larger gaps (>50 cm²). Additionally, they are manufactured with greater care and precision, according to the specific needs of each patient, and can be improved before they are inserted into the human body (Eufinger et al., 1995).

Nevertheless, implants manufactured from various materials are selected to be shaped as they are being inserted in the human body. The attributes, though, of the titanium are such that make the shaping difficult, and the implant from this material must be manufactured before the surgical operation. Lastly, a critical factor for selecting premade titanium implants is that they cover the individual needs of each patient since they have been manufactured according to their personal skull model. The manufacturing of premade titanium implants is achieved with the use of computer-aided manufacturing techniques (CAD/CAM-techniques) and computer-aided design, based on data from helical computed tomography (Figure 4.2) (Hutmacher, 2001, Lee et al., 2013). Geometrical data from CAD systems directs a Computer Numerical Control (CNC) milling machine, which manufactures the titanium implant from a larger titanium piece (Callister and Rethwisch, 2007). The disadvantage, in this phase, is that only a very small part of the larger titanium piece is used, and the rest is useless. The processing of the material to create complex forms is also difficult. This renders the titanium processing described above, costly. CAD data can be used to estimate the size of titanium micro-screws, which stabilize the implant in the skull and to design the steadying microplates (Lee et al., 2013, Ye et al., 2010).

Figure 4-2 Design and virtual application of a titanium implant with the procedure (Tomography – Image – CAD/CAM - TICC). Small holes can be seen in the implant, near its edges, where microplates and micro -screws will be applied for its steadying on the human skull

4.2 Organic Biomaterials

4.2.1. High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE)

The polymer created by heating ethylene, in the presence of oxygen and under high pressure. It is a thermoplastic material with large tolerance to chemicals.

Polyethylene used as skull implant has a porous structure and high density. It allows the growth of soft tissues in the interior of the implant due to its interconnected and properly sized pores. It is included among bioactive biomaterials. The material's nature allows its cutting and shaping with a sharp instrument without affecting the structure of its pores. The average of its pores' size does not exceed 100 micrometers, and the volume they occupy in the implant is about 50%. The growth of soft tissues in the interior of the implant varies according to the way and the area it is applied on, in the human skull (Manjila et al., 2013). Its molecular weight, which is checked during the polymerization, varies from 1000 to 38000 Mr. The molecular weight polyethylene requires to replace the skull bone is about 21000, and this is what defines its attributes and its characteristics. Polyethylene is chemically inactive. It is a poor conductor of cold, heat, and electricity. It is insoluble from bodily fluids. It retains the form it has been given and thus, does not cause injuries due to its distortion. It retains its physical and chemical stability inside the host tissue. It does not cause inflammations, infections, and toxic reactions. There is no possibility of creating sarcomas or carcinomas. It is a very strong material with elasticity and can withstand strains. It is not affected by the changes in the body's temperature. The material becomes amorphous at 115°C. Tensile modulus: 11.7 GPa.

Its fundamental disadvantages are:

- It is a foreign body that cannot be replaced by a natural bone and can cause infection
- It requires much time to be formed and is placed on the patient for a better cosmetic effect and to ensure its stability
- It is very susceptible to microorganisms due to its porous structure (Yeo et al., 2014).

The skull implant made of polyethylene is removed from a larger piece of the material. The size of the pieces commercially available are: small (38 mm x 13 mm x 3 mm), medium (50 mm x 25 mm x 6 mm), and large (63mm x 38 mm x 9.5 mm). For larger

skull gaps, the material is available in 107 mm x 97 mm x 6 mm, in an arched form. The surgeon gives the final shape to the implant by cutting it and then smoothing it with various medical cutting tools (sharp scalpels, surgical and scissors). During the cutting procedure, the interconnection and the structure of the material's pores are not altered. Additionally, the surgeon has the capability to give the required archness to the material by immersing it in sterile serum at 180°F, for a few minutes. After it forms it, it is immersed into a frozen sterile serum to make it harder and to make it retain the form given. The solidification of the implant on the skull is achieved with micro-screws from the same material. After the solidification on the patient's skull, the surgeon can give a sophisticated shape to the implant for a better cosmetic result. (Figure 4.3) (Manjila et al., 2013).

Figure 4-3 Shaping procedure for a polyethylene implant.

The designs and moulds required for the creation of personalized geometry of skull implants made of polyethylene are manufactured with stereolithography data and CT data from the patients. The personalized implants are chiefly used for the restoration of large and complex skull gaps (Figure 4.4) (Manjila et al., 2013).

Figure 4-4 Skull implants with personalized geometry made of polyethylene.

4.2.2 Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA)

Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) is a thermoplastic polymeric material that results through the polymerization of monomer methacrylate methyl. PMMA is implemented in additive cranioplasty, particularly in the area of the forehead and the front vault. PMMA is a mortar viscosity that can be transformed into a very hard and durable plastic material. As an implant, it is relatively biocompatible, non-allergenic and non-absorbable by the organism, resistant in pressure and elasticity (tensile modulus 2.24 – 3.24 GPa), more than the natural bone, thus resulting in the efficient protection of the brain. It is also a light material, ray-permeable, and a poor conductor of heat and electricity (Eufinger et al., 1995). It does not react with bodily fluids and tissues and has excellent chemical stability inside the body. PMMA is widely accessible, and has low cost (Profeta and Huppa, 2016).

The weaknesses of the PMMA implant are relevant to its behavior inside the human organism, with its bioadaptability. The PMMA implant is considered a foreign matter by the organism and can cause inflammation to the healthy tissues, thermal and toxic reactions (Callister and Rethwisch, 2007). Studies have shown that PMMA implants inside the human body are covered with a fibrous membrane, which is not vascular, and thus, does not allow the growth of tissue in their interior. Thus, chronic inflammatory reactions in human cells are being developed in the common surface between the implant

and the neighboring tissues. This case can cause carcinogenesis (Profeta and Huppa, 2016), and its removal is necessary (Callister and Rethwisch, 2007). However, the removal of the implant, when required, is very difficult, because it tends to melt when it is cut, or its milling is attempted, with power tools (Profeta and Huppa, 2016).

There are two types of PMMA. The first one is polymerized slowly (more than 24 hours), with an external procedure involving heating and pressing. The second one is polymerized immediately, with an exothermic chemical reaction. The reaction occurs simultaneously with the placement and the shaping of the material in the patient's skull. However, the second type can even cause death to the patient, because, due to the exothermic reaction, high temperatures are produced that can cause necrosis of the neighboring healthy bone tissue and part of the dura mater (Yeo et al., 2014). The PMMA implant that is polymerized in few minutes has pores in its interior with a diameter of 0.25 to 0.5 mm. Polymer residues also appear. These implants have less mechanical strength due to the pores (Profeta and Huppa, 2016).

*Figure 4-5 PMMA manufacturing method a) Ingredients: liquid and power,
b) Mixing the ingredients in an open cup
c) Applying the mixture to the skull's frontal area (Fu et al., 2016)*

This method of manufacturing and placing the implant requires sculptural abilities from the operating neurosurgeon, familiarity with the material's attributes and extensive experience in its use. Nevertheless, there is a likelihood of misplacement of the implant, due to the little allocated time the doctor has, and of the final, particularly cosmetic, outcome being disappointing (Manjila et al., 2013).

The above method of manufacturing and inserting PMMA implants can cause significant issues with the patient's health. The solution proposed is the manufacturing and the geometrical shaping of the implants, according to the individual needs of each patient, before the operation (Figure 4.6). For the implementation of this solution, CAD/CAM techniques are being used. Using such techniques, the operational time, the possibility of an infection, and, consequently, the total cost are reduced (Callister and Rethwisch, 2007).

The pre-manufactured PMMA implants are being used to restore large gaps (>50 cm²). In such gaps, it is difficult to give the appropriate symmetry and precision to the implants, in the brief allocated time of the surgical operation. Even more so when the gap is situated in the front part of the front vault, where there are increased cosmetic demands. Lastly, a significant factor in selecting this method is that the pre-manufactured implants satisfy the individual needs of each patient since they have been manufactured according to his individual skull model (Eufinger et al., 1995). Although the advantages of this method are many, issues like the one with the biocompatibility of the implant's material cannot be solved with any method of insertion in the human organism (Merlino and Carlucci, 2015).

Figure 4-6 The procedure of the preparation of the pre-manufactured PMMA implant includes four stages: 1) CT scanning, 2) processing the CT data with a computer, 3) manufacturing the mould and 4) manufacturing the implant (Figure 4.7) (Eufinger et al., 1995).

Figure 4-7 Pre-manufactured PMMA implant (Eufinger et al., 1995).

Figure 4-8 The implant is applied with microplates made of titanium (Callister and Rethwisch, 2007).

4. 3 Ceramic Biomaterials

Ceramic materials and particularly those made of calcium phosphate ones have been widely used for the restoration of skull gaps. Calcium phosphate has been implemented in the form of artificial bones. It can be crystallized to salts, like hydroxylapatite, depending on the analogy Ca:P, the presence of water and admixtures, and the temperature. In a liquid environment, and at low temperatures ($< 900^{\circ}\text{C}$) hydroxyl or

hydroxylapatite are formed. Both of these forms are especially biocompatible with the tissues and are used as a compact solid or as bone substitutes in granular shape. The demanding nature of calcium phosphate is considered to be closely tied with the mineral phase of teeth and bones. Calcium phosphate ($\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$) is the main ingredient of bones while calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) of the shells of eggs, shells and corals (An et al., 2016).

Contrary to the rest of the materials used in additive cranioplasty, calcium phosphate ones are bioactive (pipelines of bone cells) and have the capability to grow tissues in their body, and to integrate with the area of the tissue receiver after their installation. The result is that they are particularly receivable by the human organism, without creating inflammations and negative reactions to the neighboring bone tissue. CP material cannot produce bone cells on its own; it provides, however, a natural substrate, where the new bone cells produced by the neighboring bone tissue can be placed and, possibly, directed to replace the areas the implant occupies. The implant is replaced by the new bone, while the size and the space it occupies is not decreased (An et al., 2016).

The mechanical attributes of the synthetic calcium phosphate vary significantly. The broad range of the attributes of polycrystalline calcium phosphate results from the various versions of its structures and the manufacturing procedures. Depending on the final calcination conditions, calcium phosphate can become calcium hydroxyapatite (An et al., 2016, Hou et al., 2016).

4.3.1 Hydroxylapatite [$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$]

Hydroxylapatite is chemically similar to the main ingredient of hard tissues and bones in mammals. Hard tissues like bones, tooth enamel and dentin are naturally synthetics, which contain protein and hydroxylapatite, water and other organic materials. The enamel is the stiffest tissue with a tensile modulus of $E=74$ GPa and contains the most of the mineral. Compact tissues ($E=12$ to 18 GPa) and Dentin ($E=21$ GPa) contain less mineral. The Poisson ratio of synthetic hydroxylapatite or mineral is about 0.27, which is close to that of the bones ($=0.3$). It is one of the few materials classified as bioactive, which means it can help the bone to grow.

Hydroxylapatite is a thermally unstable compound, as it disintegrates in temperatures of 800 - 1200°C , depending on its stoichiometry. Furthermore, by consensus, dense hydroxylapatite does not have the mechanical strength to remain unaltered for an extensive period in an environment under great pressures and frictions.

However, it presents great attributes, like the excellent biocompatibility. Hydroxylapatite seems to create a direct chemical link with hard tissues. With the implantation of hydroxylapatite as particulates or porous parts in bones, new-netted laminates of bones are formed in 4 to 8 weeks.

Hydroxylapatite coatings are frequently applied to metallic implants to alter the attributes of the surface. In this manner, the organism "thinks" that the implant is manufactured from hydroxylapatite, a material with high biocompatibility. Without the coating, the organism would identify the foreign matter and would work to isolate it from the surrounding tissues. To date, the sole commercially acceptable method of using hydroxyapatite is the coatings in metallic implants (plasma spraying) (Aslan et al., 2012).

Hydroxylapatite can be found in different forms, such as dust or particles and can be used to fill the imperfections or the gaps in the bones. These gaps and imperfections can occur in cases where large parts of the bone must be removed (bone cancers, for example). The bone filler will provide a scaffold and will stimulate the rapid filling of the gap by shaping the bone. It will also become part of the bone structure and will reduce healing times compared to the situation where no bone filler was used (Tuncer et al., 2004).

4.3.2 Hydroxylapatite Cement – HAC

The chemical manufacturing and the convenience of placing the implant of hydroxylapatite cement make this material one of the most practical in cranioplasty. It can be easily processed and has the capability to fit perfectly in a gap. It is highly biocompatible with the bone. It is proven that it rarely causes infections or irritations and always retains its structural stability. It is non-allergenic and non-carcinogenic. It does not corrode chemically. Its microporous structure adds to the implant's mechanical strength. The diameter of the pores is 2 to 5 μm and renders the implant impermeable to cells and bacteria (Fricia et al., 2015). As for its mechanical behavior, the HAC implant is durable but also fragile (Callister and Rethwisch, 2007, Tuncer et al., 2004).

Dried hydroxylapatite cement is a crystalline powder (average size of grain 0.30 μm) consisting of two distinctive calcium phosphate salts, the tetra calcium phosphate (TTCP) and the dimethyl tetrachloro terephthalate (DCPA).

These two salts, with the presence of water (or other liquids: blood, plasma) as a catalyst are dissolved and transformed into liquid homogenous hydroxylapatite (OHAp). It is necessary for the analogy of HAC powder to be solvent and precise. The reaction lasts

for about four hours until its completion. In the first 20 minutes, after the blending with the water, the first traces of OHAp appear. However, after four hours, OHAp acquires a microporous structure that ensures the stability and the durability of the implant (An et al., 2016).

OHAp implant can be moulded and shaped as it is being placed in the skull. The material can be malleable for up to 30 minutes. It is necessary for the area of the operation to remain dry during the placement of OHAp and then, for 3 to 4 hours, to ensure the proper allocation of the OHAp crystals. In that time limit, the implant must not be exposed to any liquid, although this is not always possible in cranioplasty. If the implant is exposed to any liquid, then the desirable form is altered, and the chemical composition of the material is ruined. As a result, the implant must be removed, and the procedure must be repeated. Additionally, it is necessary for the skull's skin to remain open during these four hours, for the implant to not be exposed to bodily fluids. In this phase, there is a possibility of germs settling on the implant (Fricia et al., 2015).

The directed restoration of the bone is a procedure according to which the bone restored enriches the surface and the interior of the implanted biomaterial. This procedure can be successfully achieved by selecting the proper scaffold biomaterial. The natural image of this material depends on the shape and size of the area it will be placed.

The scaffolds manufactured with Calcium Phosphate Cements (CPC) are appropriate for the restoration of skull bones. They are utterly biocompatible and can replace a bone for a considerable period, having similar behavior to it. Additionally, CPC shows normal temperatures inside the human body, which is clinically proper. The interior architecture of the scaffold, as is size, shape, distribution, and interconnection of the pores, has a crucial role in the implant's mechanics and its function in the body. The Solid Freeform Fabrication (SFF) allows the manufacturing of porous scaffolds from CPC with a specifically selected design, size, and interconnectivity of macropores (Hou et al., 2016, Manjila et al., 2013).

In table 4.1 and 4.2 are gathered the most significant advantages and disadvantages of the four biomaterials that used as skull bone replacement.

Table 4-1 Titanium and High-Density polyethylene Advantages and Disadvantages

Titanium		High-density polyethylene	
Advantages	Disadvantages	Advantages	Disadvantages
Durability	Easy rejection	Chemically inactive	Need time to be formed
Biocompatibility	Irregular Thermal Conduction	Poor conductor of heat, cold and electricity	Need time to be placed
Retain chemical stability	Cause Headaches	Insoluble from bodily fluids	Very susceptible
	Annoying Pressure	Retain their form	
Non-carcinogenic	Not in new organism	Retain physical and chemical stability	
Non-inflammatory	Difficult to mould, cut and shape	Non-inflammatory	
Easy Manufactured	Processing quite costly	Non-toxic reaction	
Small tensile module		Non-carcinogenic	
		Strong and Elastic material	
		Not affected from temperature	

Table 4-2 Hydroxyapatite and Polymethacrylic methyl ester Advantages and Disadvantages

Hydroxylapatite		Polymethacrylic methyl ester PMMA	
Advantages	Disadvantages	Advantages	Disadvantages
Biocompatibility	Thermally unstable	Biocompatible	Cause inflammation
Chemical link with hard tissues	Not mechanical strength	Non-allergenic	Thermal and toxic reaction
Easily fill the imperfections or the gaps in the bones		Non-Absorbable	Carcinogenesis
Reduce healing times		Resistant in pressure	Melt when it is cutting
Structural stability		Elastic	
Non-carcinogenic		Light Material	
Non-allergenic		Poor conductor of heat and electricity	
		Chemical stability	
	Low cost		

Table 4-3 Cost of 3D Printer Filament

Cost of 3D Printer Filament			
Titanium (Ti)	High-density polyethylene (HDPE)	Hydroxylapatite (HAC)	Polymethacrylic methyl ester (PMMA)
Raw powder costs between £250 and £400 per kilogram	HDPE Filament (1.75mm) cost £25 per kilogram	HAC Nanopowder cost £57 per 10 gram so £5700 per kilogram	Pure PMMA Filament (1.75mm) for 3D Printers cost £30 per 1KG

Chapter 5 : Implant design for the restoration of skull bone

The objective of the application is an actual skull whose right side is damaged. Specifically, the skull belongs to a 17-year-old man who has suffered a complex fracture from a gunshot. The damaged area includes the right parietal bone, and parts of the adjacent front and temporal bones. The destroyed part of the skull has been removed and in its place, there is a gap of about 150 cm². This gap, if the patient survives, must be replaced with an artificial implant, both for the protection of the brain and the nervous system and for cosmetic reasons. The gap is large; thus, it is necessary for the implant to be pre-manufactured and designed according to the patient's measurements. Particularly, the implant that will replace the bone must have analogous mechanical rigidity and stability to the structure that is to be replaced, to have the geometrical size and shape that fits the area of its placement, and the biomaterial of the implant must be biocompatible. The design engineer gives designing solutions to the biological, mechanical, geometrical, and manufacturing restrictions. The initial data that will be studied and processed is the medical images of the skull from a computer tomography. Figure 5.1 shows the digital model of the front and the side view of the skull. The commercial software that accompanies the CT scanner directly creates this 3D model, by recomposing the 2D sections (DICOM files) in 3D space. This model is directed solely towards imaging and medical diagnosis.

Figure 5-1 3D digital model of the skull

In the following application, contemporary methods of recomposing and processing medical images will be implemented, to create a digitally processable model of the area of the gap, and of the design, and of the solid modelling of the object that will replace the particular area. In the procedure of the application, the acquiring of the object's medical data, its study, its processing and the manufacturing of the objects is described step by step. In the end, the results and the conclusions of the procedure are presented. The whole procedure is based on the tissue-engineering principals described above.

5.1 Choosing the object of the study

The choice was made considering the criteria below:

1. The importance of the restoration of the skull gap. At «G. Gennimatas» Athens General Hospital, among the 1000 surgeries performed each year, 20 are cranioplasties. Pre-manufactured and biodegradable implants are not being used in these cranioplasties.
2. Tissue engineering: The human skull, and the femur, have been used as examples of applications of the principles of tissue engineering and therefore, of the design engineer's knowledge. These examples frequently appear in scientific literature.
3. Simple anatomy: The anatomy of the human skull is relatively simple and therefore, more understandable to individuals without medical studies.
4. Area of the gap: The design engineer is tasked with giving the best cosmetic result to the restoration of the skull bone. The area of the gap on the selected object, can be processed through simple functions of CAD software, like Mirror and Boolean.
5. Mechanical requirements: The mechanical demands of the neurocranium are easier to assess than in other areas of the human skeleton, as is the case with the femur, for example. The mechanical requirements of the area of the gap the design mechanic has to give solutions to can be calculated with the use of software combined with certain mathematical operations.
6. Small file size: The rendering and the modelling of the tissue are as simple as its anatomy. This means that the number of the virtual points the digital model is comprised of is smaller, and thus, the file size is also smaller. In this study, this fact helps the processing of the object from a personal computer and its modelling as a prototype.

5.2 Collecting medical data from Computed or Computerized Axial Tomography

The data for the patient's skull is collected from a helical computed scanner (Philips Brilliance). The particular axial scanner derives the transverse section from a slightly different angle, as the scanner is revolving around the object. Then, the sections are transmitted to a computer, through local network connection, where the data is retrieved in digital form

The digital data retrieved by the computer are in DICOM (*.dcm) (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) form. DICOM is the industrial standard for transferring medical images and any medical data among imaging and diagnostic systems from different manufacturers, computing systems of medical data management and stand-alone workstations. The number of sections scanned is 515 and comprise the whole neurocranium of the patient and part of the viscerocranium, up to the upper jaw. Each section has a width of 0.4mm, and each voxel it is comprised of has a size of about 0.6 X 0.6 X 0.4mm. The DICOM files of the sections are the basis for the processing, in order to create digital and natural models. On Figure 5.2, two of the 515 transverse sections are depicted. The imaging software of these sections accompanies the CT scanner, where the data has been collected. This imaging tool is solely used for the direct imaging of transverse sections, medical diagnosis, and medical measurements.

Figure 5-2 Transverse sections in DICOM form, from a CT scanner

5.3 Input of medical data in imaging and processing software

The 515 DICOM files retrieved, were stored in an electronic file in the order they were scanned, and each one carries a different name with the extension *.dcm. Each file has a size of 534 KB. Among the 515 files, the 256 necessary files were chosen to be implemented in order to decrease the bulk of data. The 256 transverse sections comprise the whole neurocranium, up to the upper eye sockets.

The selected files were inserted into the software (Materialise's Interactive Medical Image Control System – MIMICS, Materialise). MIMICS is an interaction tool for visualizing and segmenting medical images (such as MRI and CT) and rendering 3D objects. The interactive surface of the software is similar to the ones of Windows' programs. It includes working windows where medical images, menu bars, tool buttons, mouse pointers, and dialogue windows for commands inserted with the keyboard are presented. The software creates a stack list where these 256 DICOM files are classified according to data that includes name and placement in the electronic folder; The sections are automatically placed in a particular order and the software can, then, perform any processing.

On Figure 5.3, the main interface of another imaging and processing of medical data software is presented. On the right section, the 256 transverse sections can be seen, on the left one selected section out of the 256 and in the centre, a window with information and dialogue, which appears after a command from the user. Inside the window, there is information regarding the voxels' dimensions in mm, which comprise each section, and the capability of changing these dimensions is provided to the user.

Figure 5-3 Interface of another imaging and medical data processing software in DICOM form

5.4 Cropping the region of interest from medical pictures of a CT scan

The term crop refers to the procedure where one or more regions of interest can be cropped and isolated from the rest of the structures depicted in an image from a tomography. Here, the hard tissues are separated from the soft tissues (bones). The purpose is the isolation of the skull for further modelling. The skull, in this case, is the region of interest (ROI) separated from the rest of the section with the semi-automatic method of cropping called thresholding, which leads to the binary classification of all the bulk data, according to the density of the objects (voxel's shade of gray). In other words, this method is based on the local homogeneity of the tissues and recognizes the edges of the areas which share borders. If in some points, the borders are not clear, and the method fails, then the outlines are re-designed or corrected by the user according to their judgment. Every 2D section is processed separately, and the interior and exterior borders of the tissues are separated by creating outlines. On Figure 5.4, the method of cropping and selecting a region of interest on MIMICS software is applied. On Figure a), three sections and their direction in the picture windows of MIMICS are presented. The areas where the shade of gray is obviously lighter than the rest are the bone tissue. Even in these areas, the compact bones, and the dipole are visible. On Figure b), the software gives a shade of green to the areas that have been set as a region of interest and considers them as an individual object for processing. Furthermore, the software automatically identifies the attributes of the area that correspond to it.

Figure 5-4 Procedure of fragmentation in MIMICS: a) 2D sections, b) separating bone tissue with the semiautomatic method of threshold cropping

On Figure 5.5, the method of cropping the region of interest in a section performed with another software is presented. During the first phase (Figure a), the software identifies the density of the color in the areas of the section. During the second phase (Figure b), the software separates the section in two areas, the one of the soft (red outline) and the one of the hard tissue (blue outline). During the third phase (Figure c), the user selects which of the two areas will be their region of interest.

Figure 5-5 Cropping procedure in another software: a) One of the 256 2D sections, b) separating hard and soft tissues using the thresholding method, c) selecting bone tissue

The software, after separating the soft from the hard tissue automatically, and after a command input by the user, identifies some of the attributes of each area. For example, in a transverse section and the area of the bone tissue, the values of the grey's density, which, by extension, are related to the density of the bone mass, are identified. In this particular case, the minimum value, the maximum value, and the average of the values of the grey's density were calculated from the 256 selected transverse sections. On Figure 5.6, the value of the average of the grey's density is visible, which is 1861.92.

Figure 5-6 The average value of the grey's density in the area of the bone tissues is calculated by the software when demanded, and requires the separation of the tissues.

After the average of the values of the grey's density is calculated, the calculation of the bone mass and, by extension, the calculation of the tensile modulus is also possible. These calculations are made with specific mathematical operations. Particularly in the case of the skull in question, applies

$$QCT\# = 1161.92 - 1024$$

$$QCT\# = 137.92 HU$$

$$\rho = 7.69 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot 137.92 + 1.028$$

$$\rho = 1.134 g/cm^3$$

$$E = 0.09 \cdot 1.134^{7.4}$$

$$E = 2.283 GPa = 2283 MPa$$

Where:

QCT# is the value of the Quantitative Computed Tomography and is measured in Hounsfield units (HU)

ρ is the value of the bone mass's density in g/cm^3 and

E is the tensile modulus in GPa.

In that fashion, the mechanical attributes of the skull were recognized. These were the density of the bone mass and its tensile modulus. These two attributes are directly related to pressure resistance, which defines how susceptible the bone is to fractures. The selection of the biomaterial that will be implemented in the manufacture of the implant

for the restoration of the gap, for the efficient protection of the brain and the neural system, is also made according to the two attributes above.

5.5 3D imaging of tomography data and volume rendering

Since the segmentation procedure has been completed, the next phase is the creation of a CAD model available for processing. The procedure begins with a 3D reconstruction of the sections and particularly of the 2D regions of interest. According to the 3D reconstruction, 2D digital images are placed near each other (paste procedure), in order to shape the volumetric model. This model consists of some elements with the bulk of a flat rectangle. On Figure 5.7 appears the digital model of the whole skull that has been scanned. MIMICS software, according to the MedCAD method, automatically creates polylines that adjust to the 3D model. These polylines can be transformed to B-spline curves and surfaces, in order to become a CAD surface model available for processing. 3d models allow the study of the third dimension. They can be seen from every direction with the non-visible lines being hidden, with variable illumination, transparency, and reflectiveness. In the models, there is also the capability to apply visualization commands, as is the adjustment of the density of contrast, focus, and rotation. Colors for the marking or the classification of various areas of the model can also be used. Lastly, the software that creates the model includes tools for providing information regarding the dimensions and size of bulk surfaces.

Figure 5-7 a) Creation of a 3D model with MIMICS software b) 3D skull model consisting of bulk volumes.

5.6 Implant model design

Since there is a CAD model composed of curves and B-Spline surfaces, the software provides a set of functions that have been used for the creation of the implant for the restoration of the skull gap. In brief, the implant was created by copying the respective area of the healthy side of the skull and adjusting it to the area of the gap. The functions that were made available by the software and implemented were reposition, mirror, cut, and split. Initially, the skull was restored in the correct position by rotation. This occurred because, during the scan, the patient was placed in a random position, which resulted in the 3D model not having correct orientation inside the software's image windows. Then, a flat element was created directly in the middle of the skull in order to separate, visually, the right from the left side. An area of the right part enough to cover the gap in the remaining part was selected and cut with the cut command. This area was reversed according to the flat level and was adjusted in the gap area Figure 5.8. The crop command was applied for the isolation of the area needed, in order to create the implant model. Lastly, with the cut command, the geometrical borders of the implant were defined. On Figure 5.9, the implant model is visible in red color.

Figure 5-8 a) The CAD model for processing, the number of pixels it comprises of is 2,852.219 and the model's size is 391,656.8122 mm³ b) the yellow model was created with the commands cut, and mirror of the green model.

Figure 5-9 The skull's implant model.

5.7 Creating and processing the STL model for rapid prototyping

In order to create prototype models of the skull and the implant with rapid prototyping technology, the models had to, initially, transform into STL form. STL models are volume models surrounded by triangles' surfaces and are compatible with the control software of the rapid prototyping machine. The above software used to process medical images incorporates algorithms for the automatic transformation of models to STL forms. On Figure 5.10, the implant's model is shown in red and the skull's model, which is in an STL form, in green. These models have been created with MIMICS software.

Figure 5-10 Implant model's data: size 144,967.83 mm³, surface 30,087.51 mm², triangles 139,944, key points 114,344

The rapid prototyping machine which will be used is an FDM type. The reason for choosing the FDM type of the RP machine is that Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) is a technology which produces rapid prototypes. The FDM system can construct any geometrical shape. The advantages of this technique are the durability of the material used, the stability of the mechanical properties and the quality of the parts produced. FDM products also offer new possibilities for direct printing of small production series. An additional advantage, is that it can build objects fabricated from a variety of material sources by printing and continuously changing the material of the printer, which allows additional user control.

The material which will be used is Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA), which is widely used in modelling, in the production of prototypes for product design and in orthopedics as mould. In addition, PMMA's advantages outweigh its disadvantages as shown in Chapter 4 Table 4.2. The advantages of PMMA are summarized in table 5.1 below:

Table 5-1 Advantages of PMMA

Advantages
Biocompatible
Non-allergenic
Non-Absorbable
Resistant in pressure
Elastic
Light Material
Poor conductor of heat and electricity
Chemical stability
Low cost 30 pounds per 1 Kg

Furthermore, as seen above in section 5.4, the required mechanical attributes of the skull, specifically the density of the bone mass and its tensile modulus, were calculated. These two attributes are directly related to pressure resistance, which defines how susceptible the bone is to fractures. The selection of the biomaterial that will be implemented in the manufacture of the implant for the restoration of the gap, for the efficient protection of the brain and the neural system, will be made according to the two attributes above. Polymethyl Methacrylate's (PMMA) density of the bone mass and its tensile modulus is shown in Table 5.2 below.

Table 5-2 Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA) properties

Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA)	
Density	1.15 – 1.19 g/cm ³
Tensile Modulus	2.2 – 3.8 GPa

In our case of the skull, we have calculated in section 5.4 the value of bone mass' density and tensile modulus as shown in the Table 5.3 bellow.

Table 5-3 Skull Model properties

Skull	
Density	$\rho = 1.134 \text{ g/cm}^3$
Tensile Modulus	$E = 2.283 \text{ GPa}$

As a result, by comparing the Table 5.2 with 5.3 we can see that the mechanical properties that we want in our skull are within the acceptable range of density and tensile modulus of the Material selected, PMMA. So PMMA is arguably the most suitable material to be chosen.

Printing preferences, particularly economy of material and time for achieving the greatest detail were not calculated in this study.

Chapter 6 : Conclusion

Tissue engineering is an interdisciplinary field. To manufacture an implant for the restoration of the skull bone, it is necessary to include an interdisciplinary team comprised of the restoration surgeon, the radiologist, the specialist in biomaterials, the design, and model manufacturing engineer. The result is a combination of cranioplasty, science of biomaterials, radiodiagnostics, designing and manufacturing with the help of a computer.

With this specific application, knowledge and findings not available in scientific literature were inferred. Also, some issues occurred that were dealt with, thanks to the simplicity of the object studied. These issues had to do with the tools, as are software and computers, supporting these new technologies. It was established that the further technological growth of these tools is necessary since the object they serve in the field of Tissue Engineering is cogently useful to the quality of life. For the technological growth and the decrease in the cost of these tools, it is necessary to motivate, initially, the medical world, through the exhibition of the capabilities of the new interdisciplinary field of Tissue Engineering.

With the above method, the digital and natural modelling of the skull and the implant is possible, by using medical images of a patient as raw material. These models can serve the following medical purposes:

- Studying of the problematic area (by a surgeon) and preparing a surgical plan before the procedure. The use of models decreases the duration of the procedure significantly, allowing the surgeon to practice on it and to correct many of the technical flaws and difficulties.
- Providing a communication tool among the medical personnel, the patient, and the designer of personalized implants.
- Directly manufacturing personalized implants with the method of rapid prototyping, using biomaterials and the appropriate equipment.
- Manufacturing tissue scaffolds as a substitute to skull tissue made from implant biomaterial, for example, hydroxylapatite
- Using the model for processing in Pro/Engineer environment for the design of moulds and the manufacture of personalized implants
- Analyzing and assessing the model and the implanted biomaterial with finite elements technology.

- Selecting an ideal biomaterial for the implant

In the past subtractive manufacturing was used to design implants for the restoration of skull bones. Subtractive manufacturing is the procedure by which the fabrication of the object is performed by cumulatively removing material until the final form is obtained.

Conversely, additive manufacturing is the procedure by which the fabrication of an object is carried out by adding only the material which is required. This process reduces the cost, the time and wastage in comparison with the subtractive manufacturing, and is consequently more productive.

Below is an analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of using 3d bioprinting technology instead of the traditional methods.

6.1 Advantages of 3D bioprinting in comparison with traditional methods

Personalized medicine

Through 3D printing, each patient who needs a slightly different variation of one of their body parts will be able to receive it immediately. Hospitals will print what the patient needs for a surgical operation, and will replace, each time, the appropriate part or in our case, parts of the skull. Lastly, they will have the capability to print the appropriate medical equipment for each patient's case, which can be complicated or expensive for each procedure (Ventola, 2014).

Accessibility

In the past, only specialists and professionals had access to this technology. The portable 3D printer is accessible almost everywhere, such as in hospitals and physicians' offices.

Affordable prices

As its accessibility becomes wider, it allows everybody to benefit from this emerging technology. Thus, as the variety and the competition will grow, the pricing of 3D printers will lead to an increase in the number of users interested in it.

Improved quality of life and prosperity

3D printing has the capability to increase quality of life and prosperity, since any basic part or model used in the fields of medicine and health, can be easily developed. Furthermore, it also has ecological benefits, since 3D printing is considered friendly to the environment because it produces less waste compared to other techniques.

Faster production cycles

With 3D printing, many of the middle stages in the production procedure are deemed unnecessary. Not only will the manufacturing of objects (the skull, for example) become easier, it will also improve accessibility significantly, even in remote areas. Imagine that there is a patient with an issue with his skull, in a remote area. With the use of 3D printers, there will be a capability to print a part of the skull, with low cost. This can strengthen production with the manufacturing of a large number of prototypes, in less time than conventional methods (Bose et al., 2013).

Democratisation of bioprinting

A feature of 3D printing, much appreciated by the scientific community, is the democratisation of the design. Frequently, scientific researchers have to face the issue of the compatibility among files, due to the large volume of data collected and interpreted by different software. Thus, the exchange of data among hospitals, medical practices, and personnel is hindered. Maintaining an open-source database of 3D printing will allow everyone to download the available designs in .stl format, which will benefit the deployment of the technology. Identifying the value of transparency and exchange, the National Institute of Health in Greece has set up the 3D Print Exchange, to inspire users to share 3D print files, such as custom laboratory equipment, anatomical models, and replicas of proteins, bacteria and viruses (Ventola, 2014).

Less waste

In numerous cases, the manufacturing procedure requires that the operator starts with a quantity of material, much larger than the one needed for the finished product. The product must be carved and formed in order to take its final shape, leaving much-unused material. Although there are many strategies for the implementation of the excess material on such occasions, it is far better to avoid waste than attempt to repurpose it. Since, the

majority of 3D printing contains the layering of materials, a skull or a part of it can be manufactured with less or even nonexistent excess material.

6.2 Disadvantages of 3D bioprinting in comparison with traditional methods

- Uncontrolled or lawless manufacturing of body parts, medical equipment or food
- Perverse disincentives regarding health: If everything can be substituted, why live a healthy life?

Feasibility of Use in the Real World

Ideally, in the future, 3D printers will be installed at all major surgical centres, however, presently there are several difficulties to be overcome if this is to be achieved. There is the price of the printer and the materials needed, as well as the operating costs involved when the process takes an extended period of time to be completed. In terms of manpower, a technician will require skilled technical training and a period of supervised practice before he/she becomes a competent operator of the printer, a time consuming and expensive process (Kietzmann et al., 2015).

Loss of Manufacturing Jobs

With additional manufacturing occurring within the house, the office, or in single factories instead of several, many associated working positions will cease. Although this is the case with any new technology, it is still a cause for alarm, since the actual extent of the phenomenon cannot be determined in advance.

Energy Consumption

3D printers provide factories with the capability to remove shipping steps and shut down parts of their operations. However, the procedure still requires significant amounts of energy, because it is rather slow and printers need to be operating non-stop for many hours or days at a time. This causes significant consumption of energy, especially in cases where large printers are necessary in order to fulfill the most complex tasks. This means that, eventually, the cost of this energy consumption will be passed over to customers and small companies operating from their homes or offices (Savastano et al., 2016).

Ethical issues

The consideration of ethical implications surrounding 3D bio-printing will need to be addressed as the technique becomes more widely available. Lifestyle implications such as, whether the availability of new organs 'on demand' will discourage people from leading a healthy life - why control alcohol intake when a new liver can be had without ever going on a transplant list? Will this treatment be universally available or only for those who can afford it? Who will have ultimate control over these decisions? Will criminals be able to use bioprinting to their advantage and avoid capture by printing skin with new fingerprints or having radical facial reconstruction?

6.3 Future Research

Two crucial developments are scheduled to happen at the next stages. Progress in 3D image based restoration and virtual reality will lead to quicker data processing - decreasing processing times. Availability to surgeons of real-time navigation systems to surgeons will be utilised for the accurate placement of compound designed implants using virtual reality and visualization.

There is an extensive range of differences in the mechanical properties between the titanium load tray, the bone graft and the skull implant itself. In the future, there will be a new generation of hybrid metal-polymers from which the new implants will be constructed. These will have mechanical properties closer to natural bone, which will be replaced partially or even entirely by native tissue ingrowth. All the above stated functional requirements would be combined to replace the lost anatomical structure.

In addition, in the future, any speciality that occurs as per needs of each patient it will be treated. Engineers and Surgeons are working towards the development of the creation of a new specialisation as bio-CAD/CAM. These engineers will continue working for the potential evolution of specific patient implant that will imitate not only the form as it exists today but also to have mechanical, chemical and physiological properties similar to natural tissues – that can change and offer an environment for cell differentiation and growth.

The common biomaterials presently being used have not changed during recent years even with the introduction of bioceramics that are osteoconductive and biopolymers, that have similar mechanical properties to natural tissues. There is no one single material which can provide a solution to every patient's individual problem. In the future, there

will be a regenerative pharmaceutical application which allows the growth of natural tissues similar to those in the area of implantation. Advances in material science and the synthesis of tissues and bones will guide a new generation of designer implants that can be individualised for each patient. Furthermore, in the field of additive manufacturing, the manufacturing process will head in a new direction eliminating the problem of shape and structure and creating parts that will be the future of custom implants. Future developments will also broaden the range of materials suitable for these purposes. To sum up, the future will see new blends of alloplastic and autologous materials that will be used in combination to create the next generation of cranial bone implants.

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